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AFRICA IN GLOBAL TRADE: AFRICA CONTINENTAL FREE TRADE AREA TO THE RESCUE

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Abstract

The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) presents a major opportunity for African countries to bring 30 million people out of extreme poverty and to raise the incomes of 68 million others who live on less than \$5.50 per day. With the implementation of AfCFTA, trade facilitation measures that cut red tape and simplify customs procedures would drive \$292 billion of the \$450 billion in potential income gains. Implementing AfCFTA would help usher in the kinds of deep reforms necessary to enhance long-term growth in African countries. The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) agreement will create the largest free trade area in the world measured by the number of countries participating. The pact connects 1.3 billion people across 55 countries with a combined gross domestic product (GDP) valued at US\$3.4 trillion. But achieving its full potential will depend on putting in place significant policy reforms and trade facilitation measures. The scope of AfCFTA is large. The agreement will reduce tariffs among member countries and cover policy areas such as trade facilitation and services, as well as regulatory measures such as sanitary standards and technical barriers to trade. Full implementation of AfCFTA would reshape markets and economies across the region and boost output in the services, manufacturing and natural resources sectors. As the global economy is in turmoil due to the COVID-19 pandemic, creation of the vast AfCFTA regional market is a major opportunity to help African countries diversify their exports, accelerate growth, and attract foreign direct investment.

Keywords

AfCFTA, Global Trade, African Union, African Economic Growth and Development

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INTRODUCTION

The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) is a free trade area encompassing most of Africa (Loes Witschge, 2018) It was established in 2018 by the African Continental Free Trade Agreement, which has 43 parties and another 11 signatories, making it the largest free-trade area by number of member states, after the World Trade Organization, and the largest in population and geographic size, spanning 1.3 billion people across the world's second largest continent (Justina Crabtree, 2018).

The agreement founding AfCFTA was brokered by the African Union (AU) and signed by 44 of its 55 member states in Kigali, Rwanda on 21 March 2018 . The proposal was set to come into force 30 days after ratification by 22 of the signatory states. On 29 April 2019, the Saharawi Republic made the 22nd deposit of instruments of ratification, bringing the agreement into force on May 30; it entered its operational phase following a summit on 7 July 2019, and officially commenced 1 January 2021. AfCFTA's negotiations and implementation are overseen by a permanent secretariat based in Accra ([Ghana Abdi Latif Dahir, 2019](#)).

Under the agreement, AfCFTA members are committed to eliminating tariffs on most goods and services over a period of 5, 10, or 13 years, depending on the country's level of development or the nature of the products. General long-term objectives include creating a single, liberalized market; reducing barriers to capital and labour to facilitate investment; developing regional infrastructure; and establishing a continental customs union. The overall aims of AfCFTA are to increase socioeconomic development, reduce poverty, and make Africa more competitive in the global economy ([U.S. International Trade Administration, 2022](#)).

Statement of the Problem

In the post-World War II era, globalisation of the world economy has developed at a rapid pace. This has been made possible by increase in economic activities such as international trade and foreign direct investment (FDI). The pace of globalisation was also quickened by the multilateral trade negotiations under the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT). According to [Urata \(2002\)](#), beginning in the 1990s, new regionalism, which is economic in character, became a common feature in the world and Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) have played a central role in the inclination towards regional integration. Globalisation of the world economy, especially in the areas of trade, production and finance, has made the world more interconnected and integrated ([Heywood, 2011](#)). This has led to the weakening of the autonomy of states, since financial markets are volatile in nature and affects national economies. In order for states to resist the pressures of globalisation, African states, most of which are small and vulnerable, saw the formation of regional groupings as a panacea to effects of globalisation. One major feature of globalisation is the proliferation of FTAs ([Urata, 2002](#)). Due to trade liberalization, countries are negotiating to bring down trade barriers by the use of bilateral and multilateral FTAs. More significantly, the retreat of the US and the United Kingdom, two major powers of the post-world war II era, who were the architects of the United Nations, the Bretton Woods Institutions (namely the World Bank and International Monetary Fund) and the multilateral trading system provided an opportunity for African countries to reflect on the system of multilateralism and its implications for regional integration in Africa. It is in this light that African leaders conceived, negotiated and adopted the AfCFTA ([Ismail, 2019](#)).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

What is the AfCFTA?

The AfCFTA is an ambitious trade pact to form the world's largest free trade area by creating a single market for goods and services of almost 1.3bn people across Africa and deepening the economic integration of Africa. The trade area could have a combined gross domestic product of around \$3.4 trillion, but achieving its full potential depends on

significant policy reforms and trade facilitation measures across African signatory nations (1st Fiduciary (2023)).

Operationalization of AfCFTA

On January 13, 2022, the AfCFTA took a major step towards its objective with the establishment of the Pan-African Payment and Settlement System (PAPSS), which allows payments among companies operating in Africa to be done in any local currency (U.S. International Trade Administration, 2022). In April 2024, the African Union announced that the AfCFTA entered into its operational phase of the agreement. The operational phase, which effectively puts the agreement into force, is characterized by the following actions:

- Establishment of the rules of origin, which will govern the conditions a product or service can be traded duty free;
- Tariff concessions, 90% tariff liberalization;
- Online mechanism, allows members to report non-tariff barriers;
- Pan-African payment and settlement system, allows certainty of payments and will instill confidence in the system
- African Trade Observatory, a portal to address hindrances to trade, will be provided by AU member states.

Other Advances in Implementation of the AfCFTA

- On 10 March 2023, the AfCFTA Secretariat and Afrexim bank announced the launch of the AfCFTA Adjustment Fund. The Adjustment Fund consists of a Base Fund, a General Fund, and a Credit Fund, which will work together to support African countries and the private sector as they adjust to the new trading conditions. According to Afrexim bank, the \$10bn fund will help to mitigate potential adverse effects of the tariff losses many countries will suffer and to address infrastructure deficits and supply chain bottlenecks that impede implementation of the AfCFTA.
- The Pan-African Payment and Settlements System was launched by Afrexim bank in September 2021 with the support of the AfCFTA Secretariat. It is a continent-wide platform for processing, clearing and settling intra-African payments, designed to enable individuals, businesses and governments to make instant cross-border payments in the more than 40 different African currencies, thereby reducing the need for US dollars and other hard currencies and so, simplifying cross-border trade. Its launch and operation create important advantages for the African banking sector.
- Afrexim bank is currently assisting the African Regional Standards Organization to harmonize – automotive, pharmaceuticals and medical equipment – with work also under way with regard to textiles. These sectors are seen as key to boosting manufacturing in Africa, thereby reducing imports from the rest of the world.

Theoretical Framework

Dependency Theory

Interpreting and Contextualizing Dependency Theory for Patrick Bond, the simplest explanation of dependency theory is that the North gets richer the more it exchanges with the South, which in turn gets poorer because of a value transfer (Ibrahim Abdi Hassan, 2023). This value transfer happens as African countries import capital and consumer goods with high surplus value while they export local products with low value. A more complex

version of dependency theory, which was worked out in Brazil among other places, articulates the problems related to dependent and weak economies without the ability to form backward-forward linkages. For Bond, the 1980s brought in new ways of understanding uneven development that contributed with interesting insights about extreme inequalities in Africa, among other things. A core understanding on dependency theory has also been developed based on an examination of colonial power relations in Africa, dating from King Leopold's Congo, the plantation systems, and settler colonial taxes, to exploitation related to multinationals of this day.

Samir Amin (2017) picked up these ideas and improved on dependency theory. Bond believes the theory remains relevant even more so today because the North-South system of extraction is more extreme and complex, for example due to international trade. Explanatory Power of Dependency Theory The explanatory power and the relevance of dependency theory lie in its ability to show and explain power relations. A number of examples can demonstrate how the theory remains relevant. Bond referred to HIV/AIDS which he considers to be one of the biggest threats to Africa. he noted that drugs for AIDS, which were developed in the North, were heavily priced in the 1980s and 1990s at 15 000 USD per person per year. African countries depended on the North for HIV/AIDS medication and this syphoned off their financial resources. Today, however, most African governments have facilities with the United Nations that allow for access to AIDS medicines for free after some heavy advocacy. Bond also drew on other examples to which dependency theory can be applied. He referred to the Zimbabwean migrant labour system. Northern capitalist systems with sophisticated extraction systems like mining houses or big plantations can find ways of attracting African labour that is ultra-cheap, and they usually depend on women who are reproducing labour power and subsidizing the capitalist system through their social production. Dependency continues to manifest itself in a variety of forms, including the manner in which medical and pension systems are developed and executed, with greater benefits accruing to big multinationals rather than to workers. For Bond, such cases underscore the continued relevance of dependency theory. Dependency theory is even more relevant if we are to understand the relationship of Africa with the BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa). Bond notes that this relationship can be contextualized within dependency theory in two ways. Firstly, the systems of exploitation are more amplified because when the Chinese, Brazilians, Indians, Russians and South Africans work in Africa they are more extreme and exploitative than Western countries. The latter have systems of accountability, shareholders, corporate responsibility and there are even groups that campaign against systems seen as unjust which are imposed by the World Bank and other international institutions. Such involvement is limited when it comes to BRICS and their relations with Africa. It seems BRICS countries' main objective is simply extraction and maximum exploitation.

Limitations of Dependency Theory

Despite its explanatory power in understanding the operations of multinationals, there has been a very low subscription to the theory by scholars over the years. This can be attributed, explains Bond, to how mainstream economics conceptualizes theory. For him, the discipline of economics is so censorious that it is impossible to have a healthy 70 discussions on issues of global power relations and their impact on African economic development. Usually, Bond explains, these issues are discussed on the side-lines and not in mainstream economics discussions. To increase interest among economists in dependency theory, Bond proposes that the theory should be discussed in relationship to structural

inequalities as well as the concept of uneven and combined development. In this way, dependency theory would be more robust to changing trends.

Why Does Africa Need The AfCFTA?

Trade integration across the African continent has long been limited by outdated border and transport infrastructure and a patchwork of differing regulations across dozens of markets. (Karabo Mokgonyana & Michlene Mongae, 2023)

Governments have often erected trade barriers to defend their markets from regional competition, making it more expensive for countries to trade with near neighbours than countries much further afield. Intra-African exports were 16.6% of total exports in 2017, compared with 68.1% in Europe, 59.4% in Asia, 55% in America and 7% in Oceania, according to UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). Intra-African trade, defined as the average of intra-African exports and imports, was around 2% during the period 2015–17.

The share of exports from Africa to the rest of the world ranged from 80% to 90% in 2000-17 – only Oceania had a higher export dependence on the rest of the world in that period.

What are the Predicted Economic Benefits of the AfCFTA?

In a 2020 report, the World Bank estimated that by 2035, real income gains from full implementation of the agreement could be 7%, or nearly \$450bn. By 2035, the volume of total exports would increase by almost 29% relative to business as usual. Intra-continental exports would increase by more than 81%, while exports to non-African countries would rise by 19%.

The Bank predicts that the agreement could contribute to lifting an additional 30 million people from extreme poverty and 68 million people from moderate poverty. Yet the impact across countries will not be uniform. The World Bank says that at the very high end, countries like Côte d'Ivoire and Zimbabwe could see income gains of 14% each. At the low end, some – such as Madagascar, Malawi, and Mozambique – would see real income gains of only around 2%.

In a follow-up report published in June 2022, the Bank listed benefits from the expected increase of foreign direct investment (FDI) expected to accrue from the agreement.

Under an “AfCFTA FDI broad scenario” it predicts that Africa may record an increase of 111% in FDI, further boosting real income gains in Africa to about 8% in 2035.

Under an “AfCFTA FDI deep scenario” it examines the additional gains that could result from expanding the agreement from trade in goods and services to harmonizing policies on investment, competition, e-commerce, and intellectual property rights.

Under this scenario it predicts an increase in FDI of 159% and that income gains could increase by up to 9% by 2035.

Other potential benefits of the AfCFTA highlighted by the June 2022 report include:

- Higher-paid, better-quality jobs, with women seeing the biggest wage gains.
- Wages rises of 11.2% for women and 9.8% for men by 2035, albeit with regional variations depending on the industries that expand the most in specific countries.

- Under deep integration, a rise in Africa's exports to the rest of the world of 32% by 2035, while intra-African exports would grow by 109%, led by manufactured goods.

In its Economic Development in Africa Report 2021, the UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) said that "the total untapped export potential of intra-African trade is around \$21.9 billion, equivalent to 43 per cent of intra-African exports" [Economic Development in Africa Report \(2021\)](#).

"More than one third of that export potential is explained by frictions, namely, static untapped export potential, which implies that \$8.6 billion in trade could be realized by engaging actively in efforts to identify and address current market frictions in African trade today," said the report.

How will the AfCFTA Work with Existing Regional Trade Areas in Africa?

The majority of existing intra-African trade is carried out within the continent's regional economic communities, which include the Common Market for East and South Africa (COMESA), the East African Community (EAC), the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and the South African Development Community (SADC), among others.

According to the African Union, the Regional Economic Commissions (RECs) have developed individually and each has its own distinct arrangements, but their common purpose is to facilitate regional economic integration, and they are "increasingly involved in coordinating African Union (AU) Member States' interests in wider areas such as peace and security, development and governance.

The AfCFTA Agreement recognizes the RECs as the "building blocks for the AfCFTA". As the Agreement envisages that countries which have already attained higher elimination of trading or customs barriers as members of RECs "shall maintain such higher levels among themselves, while the Protocol on Trade in Goods says that "State Parties that are members of other RECs, which have attained among themselves higher levels of elimination of customs duties and trade barriers than those provided for in this Protocol, shall maintain, and where possible improve upon, those higher levels of trade liberalization among themselves.

According to an analysis by the World Bank, in the policy areas already covered by the RECs, the AfCFTA will offer a common regulatory framework, reducing market fragmentation created by different sets of rules.

Secondly, the AfCFTA will be an opportunity to regulate policy areas important for economic integration that are often regulated in trade agreements but that so far have not been covered in most of Africa's RECs, which the Bank says "tend to be shallow".

What does the AfCFTA say about the free movement of people?

Policymakers say that the free movement of labour will be a key contributor to the successful functioning of the free trade area, but not all African countries are committed to the concept.

Alongside the signing of the AfCFTA agreement and the supporting Kigali Declaration, 30 African nations signed the Protocol on Free Movement of Persons which seeks to establish a visa-free zone within the AfCFTA countries. However, major AfCFTA signatories Nigeria and South Africa have not signed the Protocol and the political will to do so is lacking.

Can The AfCFTA Succeed?

In an interview with French Daily *Le Monde* in January 2022, African economist Carlos Lopes underlined the potential that the AfCFTA gives Africa to speak with one voice in trade negotiations.

Europe has 13 types of trade arrangements with Africa, each of which it defends firmly, he told the newspaper.

“Europe needs to understand the direction Africa is going in with the setting up of the AfCFTA... We Africans must be more united to defend our own interests,” he declared.

His comments echo those of Gyude Moore, senior policy fellow at the Center for Global Development, in the December 2020 issue of *African Business*:

“This is an African project that will require African commitment to succeed. It must proceed regardless of what happens elsewhere. We can expect external actors to continue to pursue policies that run counter to Africa’s objectives as long as such policies benefit them. Even as we have made clear our intent to move trade along a multilateral track, Africa’s largest partners may seek to pursue a bilateral one. Despite the rhetoric of Africa’s external partners, the continent’s prosperity has never been the true objective of their policies and we cannot expect that to change now.”

TOWARDS A MADE IN AFRICA REVOLUTION – BOOSTING AFRICA’S REGIONAL VALUE CHAINS

The AfCFTA is much more than a trade agreement. It should be seen as an instrument for Africa’s development. By driving the continent’s integration, the AfCFTA will result in wider and deeper regional value chain], (RVC) thereby laying foundations for a Made in Africa Revolution,” *write the authors of the AfCFTA’s 2021 Futures Report.*

As African economies seek to move away from being suppliers of raw materials to the rest of the world and towards trading more value-added products with each other, developing RVCs will enable countries to combine their comparative and competitive advantages to participate in industries from which they would otherwise be excluded.

The ability for the AfCFTA to drive this transformation in Africa is partly dependent on the successful transition from current inward-looking approaches to trade and investment towards the strengthening of RVCs where different segments of the industry value chain are located across the region reflecting local comparative advantage, say the authors.

Applying a methodological assessment of the tariff and services offers that have been exchanged amongst AfCFTA state parties, the report identifies 10 value chains where new opportunities can be maximized: Automotive; Leather and Leather Products, Cocoa; Soya; Textiles and Apparel; Pharmaceuticals; Vaccine Manufacturing; Lithium-Ion Batteries; Mobile Financial Services; and Cultural and Creative Industries.

The report aims to help governments target sectors that can benefit from their country’s entry into the AfCFTA and market players to better understand where they should invest. It also offers views from industry players running exporting enterprises in some of the value chains identified, all in the service of creating a Made in Africa revolution.

KEY FINDINGS

The African Continental Free Trade Agreement represents a major opportunity for countries to boost growth, reduce poverty, and broaden economic inclusion. Implementing AfCFTA would:

- Lift 30 million Africans out of extreme poverty and boost the incomes of nearly 68 million others who live on less than \$5.50 a day;
- Boost Africa's income by \$450 billion by 2035 (a gain of 7 percent) while adding \$76 billion to the income of the rest of the world.
- Increase Africa's exports by \$560 billion, mostly in manufacturing.
- Spur larger wage gains for women (10.5 percent) than for men (9.9 percent).
- Boost wages for both skilled and unskilled workers—10.3 percent for unskilled workers, and 9.8 percent for skilled workers.

Under AfCFTA, extreme poverty would decline across the continent—with the biggest improvements in countries with currently high poverty rates.

- West Africa would see the biggest decline in the number of people living in extreme poverty—a decline of 12 million (more than a third of the total for all of Africa).
- Central Africa would see a decline of 9.3 million.
- Eastern Africa would see a decline of 4.8 million.
- Southern Africa would see a decline of 3.9 million.
- Countries with the highest initial poverty rates would see the biggest declines in poverty rates.
- In Guinea-Bissau, the rate would decline from 37.9 percent to 27.7 percent
- In Mali, the rate would decline from 14.4 percent to 6.8 percent.
- In Togo, it would decline from 24.1 percent to 16.9 percent.

Of the \$450 billion in income gains from AfCFTA, \$292 billion would come from stronger trade facilitation—measures to reduce red tape and simplify customs procedures.

- Tariff liberalization is important, but by itself it would boost the continent's income by just 0.2 percent.
- Adding trade facilitation to the mix—including measures to reduce red tape, simplify customs procedures, and make it easier for African businesses to integrate into global supply chains—would boost the income gains by \$292 billion.
- These gains will require major efforts by countries to reduce the burden on businesses and traders to cross borders, quickly, safely, and with minimal interference by officials.

The World Bank report is designed to guide policymakers in implementing policies that can maximize the agreement's potential gains while minimizing risks.

- Creating a continent-wide market will require a determined effort to reduce all trade costs. In general, this will require legislation and regulations to enable the free flow of goods, capital and information across borders; create competitive business environments that can boost productivity and investment; and promote increased

foreign competition and foreign direct investment that can raise productivity and innovation by domestic firms.

- In a few sectors facing job losses, governments will need to be ready to support workers with adequate safety nets and policies to retrain workers.
- Governments will need to design policies to increase the readiness of their workforces to take advantage of new opportunities.

Achieving the gains from AfCFTA is especially important due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which is expected to cause up to \$79 billion in output losses in Africa in 2020 alone.

- COVID-19 has caused major disruptions to trade across the continent, including in critical goods such as medical supplies and food.
- By increasing regional trade, lowering trade costs and streamlining border procedures, full implementation of AfCFTA would help African countries increase their resiliency in the face of future economic shocks and help usher in the kinds of deep reforms that are necessary to enhance long-term growth.

CONCLUSION

Trade integration across Africa has long been limited by outdated infrastructure and differing regulations across dozens of markets. Intra-African exports were 16.6% of total exports in 2017, compared with 68.1% in Europe, 59.4% in Asia, 55% in America and 7% in Oceania.

When fully implemented, the AfCFTA will be the world's biggest largest free trade area, with a combined gross domestic product of around \$3.4 trillion. Fifty-four of the continent's 55 countries are signatories to its founding agreement.

Real Income Gains

The AfCFTA is projected not only to lead to job creation, poverty alleviation, improved welfare and sustainable development but also to ensure inclusivity for women and youth, development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and overall industrialization of the continent, guided by Agenda 2063, the AU's master plan for transforming Africa into the global powerhouse of the future.

The World Bank has estimated that by 2035, real income gains from full implementation of the AfCFTA could be nearly \$450bn. It has also suggested that Africa could see a rise in foreign direct investment by up to 159%, and a rise in exports to the rest of the world of 32%, while intra-African exports could grow by 109%, led by manufactured goods.

Turning Vision into Reality

Limited trading under the AfCFTA began in January 2021, but achieving its full potential depends on significant policy reforms and trade facilitation measures across the signatory nations, for which negotiations are still ongoing.

In order to turn this vision into reality, the main objective of the AU's designated theme is to secure the commitment of all stakeholders to speed up the implementation of the AfCFTA in 2023 and fast-track the overall economic integration of agenda of the continent.

“The Theme of the Year and its mandate to support the implementation of the AfCFTA Agreement will aim to be celebrated through close collaboration with all relevant organs and specialized agencies of the African Union, regional mechanisms and Regional Economic Communities (RECs), in line with their respective mandates to fast track the implementation of the AfCFTA for the benefit of Africa’s population,” says the African Union.

Africa Day is an annual celebration of the achievements and potential of the African continent which is celebrated in Africa and countries round the world. Its date – May 25 – commemorates the founding of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), the precursor of the current African Union. This year marks the 60th anniversary of the signature of its founding charter in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

What Nigeria tend to Gain as a Signatory to AfCFTA

On July 7, 2019, Nigeria signed the Africa Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) agreement¹ – the world’s largest free trade area deals since the formation of the World Trade Organization. The AfCFTA aims to, among other cardinal objectives, boost intra-regional trade which stands in favour of Nigeria and improve its low bilateral trade with other African countries. According to the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS), exports from Nigeria to the rest of Africa accounted for 13.2% of total exports in 2018, far below 43.9% and 27.9% to Europe and Asia respectively; also, imports from other African countries made up only 3.5% of total imports, unrivalled with 41% and 44% from Europe and Asia respectively. By signing the AfCFTA which removes tariff on about 90% of the commodities produced within Africa, trade between Nigeria and other African countries could potentially increase to 52% by 2022. However, the extent to which Nigeria would reap the encompassing benefits of the CFTA depends strongly on the improvement in efficiency of local firms, and the development of continent-wide systems upon which trade can thrive. To address the former, the inefficiency and opacity in border administration, and the lack of connective infrastructure will need to be dealt with. Furthermore, the Nigerian government may strongly consider signing the Protocol on free movement of people, which stipulates visa-free entry for up to 30 days for African nationals and the introduction of an ‘African passport’ issued by member states, that opened up for signature in March 2018 and has been signed by 32 countries.

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